

Characteristic Components in Cornus officinalis to AGEs Injury Protective Effect and Mechanism of HUVEC

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Abstract : The present study aimed to explain the protective effect of Cornus officinalis characteristic components, under AGEs damage to HUVEC. After cultured HUVEC adhered, Cornus officinalis characteristic components such as loganin, morroniside, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid and aminoguanidine (positive control drug) hatched, after 1h the AGEs (200 mg/L) were added. After 24h, LDH, SOD, MDA, NO, ET, and AngII, TGF- β , IL-1 β , ROS in the supernatant were determined. The results showed the Cornus officinalis characteristic compounds could improve vitality of SOD, NO, reduce the MDA, ET, AngII, TGF- β , IL-1 β , ROS significantly when compared with the model group. Loganin, oleanic acid, ursolic acid, had significant protective effect on AGEs injured HUVEC. As a conclusion, characteristic components in Cornus officinalis had a positive effect after HUVEC injured by AGEs.

Keywords : Cornus officinalis, morroniside, oganin, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid

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